

Effect of Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate on Mustard Protein Fraction H₁

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The effect of sodium dodecyl sulphate on mustard protein fraction H₁ (mol wt. 173800) has been monitored by the techniques of gel filtration, viscosity and difference spectra. At low concentration of SDS (1.73–3.47 mM), H₁ undergoes aggregation and at higher concentrations (5.20–10.40 mM) it dissociates. Binding of SDS to H₁ and, hence, denaturation or unfolding was observed in presence of 12.14–13.87 mM SDS. On the other hand, partial aggregation or refolding of H₁ takes place at higher concentrations of SDS (15.60–20.80 mM).

MUSTARD (*Brassica juncea*) is an important oilseed crop and it consists essentially of two protein fractions, one of which has a high molecular weight and the other a low molecular weight. Very little work has been reported on the storage proteins of *B. juncea*^{1,2}. The high molecular weight fraction consists of five protein fractions³, and protein fraction H₁ is a glycoprotein (mol. wt. 173800) with a nutritionally good amino acid composition, particularly of sulphur containing amino acids. Thus, it can be a potential raw material for the protein foods. In view of this, we have reported the effect of denaturant sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) on mustard protein fraction H₁ to study its susceptibility to denaturation in the present communication.

Experimental

The seeds of mustard var. *Raya* RLM 619 were procured from the Department of Plant Breeding of this University. All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. The isolation and purification of protein fraction H₁ was carried out using gel filtration and ion-exchange chromatography techniques³. The protein concentration was estimated by measuring the absorbance at 280 nm using a value of $E_{1\%}^{1\text{cm}}$ 8.7.

The effect of SDS on H₁ was studied using the following techniques.

Gel filtration: Sephadex G 150 (Pharmacia, Sweden), which had been equilibrated with the 0.025 M borate buffer (pH 8.0), was packed into a column (2.5×70 cm). The protein solution (5 ml), containing the protein (~50 mg), was loaded on to the column. When the experiment was performed in the presence of SDS, the column was equilibrated

with the buffer containing the appropriate concentration of SDS and the eluting buffer also contained SDS. Fractions (5 ml) were collected and absorbance was measured at 280 nm.

Viscosity: The viscosity measurements were carried out at 30.0 ± 0.1° in a Ubbelohde viscometer having flow time of 200 s with the buffer. The reduced viscosity of the fraction H₁ was measured in presence of different concentration of SDS.

Difference spectra: Difference spectra produced by the addition of different amount of SDS to the protein were recorded in a Beckman DU-7 spectrophotometer in the range 240–300 nm.

Results and Discussion

Initially the effect of time was studied on the absorbance of fraction H₁ in the presence of 3.47 mM SDS (Fig. 1). A drastic decrease in the absorbance was recorded upto 90 min and the absorbance was almost constant during 90–210 min. Therefore, the protein solutions were kept at room temperature for 3 h after the addition of SDS.

In gel filtration experiments, H₁ gave only one peak eluting at V_e/V_0 value of 1.42 (Table 1). In the presence of 1.73 mM SDS, the peak shifted to lower value (1.0) and another minor peak was observed at 1.75 value. Shift of V_e/V_0 to the lower value suggest aggregation of the protein. The additional minor peak at 1.75 value indicates dissociation of the native protein. At the higher SDS concentrations (5.20–15.60 mM), the minor peak reduced to a shoulder and decrease in V_e/V_0 value suggested aggregation. In the presence of 15.60 and 20.80 mM SDS, the value decreased to

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Fig. 1. Effect of time on absorption spectrum of H_1 in the presence of 3.47 mM SDS

1.0 in case of major peak, whereas the shoulder due to other fraction disappeared in the presence of 20.8 mM SDS, suggesting reaggregation of the protein. Rao and Rao⁸ studied the effect of SDS on mustard 12S protein at only two concentrations (2.60 and 8.67 mM) and reported aggregation of 12S mustard protein in the presence of 2.6 mM SDS whereas 8.67 mM SDS caused dissociation of proteins into two fractions

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SDS ON GEL FILTRATION PATTERN OF H_1

Protein + SDS mM	V_e/V_o Peak	
	Major	Minor
0	1.42	—
1.73	1.00	1.75
5.20	1.08	1.45
10.40	1.16	1.45
15.60	1.00	1.25
20.80	1.00	—

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SDS ON REDUCED VISCOSITY OF PROTEIN FRACTION H_1

Protein + SDS mM	Reduced viscosity ml g ⁻¹
0	6.0
1.73	10.0
3.46	6.0
5.20	26.0
6.93	26.0
8.67	30.0
12.13	40.0
13.87	54.0
17.34	44.0
20.80	24.0

The reduced viscosity of H_1 was 6.0 ml g⁻¹ and the addition of 1.73 mM SDS increased it (Table 2). It again decreased to 6.0 ml g⁻¹ in the presence of 3.47 mM SDS. With further increase in the concentration of SDS (5.2–13.87 mM), the higher values of the viscosity indicated a conformational change of the protein. The decrease in viscosity in the presence of 13.87–20.80 mM SDS again indicates partial reaggregation.

The addition of SDS (1.73–6.93 mM) produced difference spectra with troughs at 279 nm and a shoulder at 285 nm (Fig. 2A). In the concentration range 8.67–12.13 mM SDS, there occurred a blue-shift in λ_{max} from 279 to 272 nm with troughs at

Fig. 2. (A) Difference spectra of H_1 in the presence of different concentrations of SDS; (B) Plot between ΔA_{280nm} vs SDS concentrations in case of H_1

285 and 290 nm, while no trough was observed at 279 nm. The troughs at 279 and 285 nm and a shoulder at 292 nm were observed in the presence of 13.87 to 20.80 mM SDS. The trough at 279 nm originates mainly from the exposure of the tyrosine residues, whereas the trough at 292 nm is due to tryptophan and the one at 285 nm originates from both the tyrosine and the tryptophan residues⁴. In the presence of 1.73–6.93 mM SDS, the troughs indicated perturbation of the tyrosine and the presence of tryptophan residues at the surface or on the surface of the subunits of the protein. The blue-shift in λ_{max} increased with the increase in SDS concentration from 8.67 to 12.13 mM and might be due to the binding of SDS or denaturation

of protein and is also indicative of the complete unfolding of the protein. The $\Delta A_{280\text{ nm}}$ value was found to be the maximum in the presence of 12.13 mM SDS and decreased afterwards (Fig. 2B), suggesting partial reaggregation of protein at higher concentration of SDS (17.34–20.80 mM).

The increase in the reduced viscosity and the appearance of the difference spectra can be taken as evidence of the denaturation of the protein by SDS. The aggregation of the proteins by SDS has been reported^{4,6} earlier also. It is possible that SDS anions first bind to the available cationic sites on the protein causing unfolding. The partial aggregation could then occur through hydrophobic interactions.

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